

Impact Factor: 5.19

ISSN: 2181-0664

DOI: 10.26739/2181-0664

www.tadqiqot.uz

UZBEK MEDICAL JOURNAL

Volume 4, Issue 5

2023

ISSN 2181-0664

Doi Journal 10.26739/2181-0664

ЎЗБЕК ТИББИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

4 ЖИЛД, 5 СОН

УЗБЕКСКИЙ МЕДИЦИНСКИЙ ЖУРНАЛ

ТОМ 4, НОМЕР 5

UZBEK MEDICAL JOURNAL

VOLUME 4, ISSUE 5

ТОШКЕНТ-2023

ЎЗБЕК ТИББИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

ЎЗБЕКСКИЙ МЕДИЦИНСКИЙ ЖУРНАЛ | UZBEK MEDICAL JOURNAL

№5 (2023) DOI <http://dx.doi.org/10.26739/2181-0664-2023-5>

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ISSN: 2181-0664
www.tadqiqot.uz**Kayumova Nilufar Nigmatjanovna**
Tashkent State Dental Institute**A MODERN VIEW OF THE DIAGNOSIS AND TREATMENT OF INFLAMMATORY
COMPLICATIONS IN ACUTE PURULENT ODONTOGENIC OSTITIS IN CHILDREN
(LITERATURE REVIEW)****doi** <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8402761>**ABSTRACT**

Acute purulent odontogenic periostitis of the jaws is an urgent problem in dentistry and maxillofacial surgery. Among children with acute odontogenic inflammatory processes of the maxillofacial region, a significant part are patients with purulent odontogenic ostitis. This article provides a literature review on the etiological and pathogenetic mechanisms of the development of this disease, as well as methods of diagnosis and modern tactics of treatment of patients with this pathology.

Keywords: Acute purulent odontogenic periostitis, pharmacotherapy, proinflammatory cytokines, pathogenesis, interleukin, inflammatory process.

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**СОВРЕМЕННЫЙ ВЗГЛЯД ДИАГНОСТИКИ И ЛЕЧЕНИЯ ВОСПАЛИТЕЛЬНЫХ
ОСЛОЖНЕНИЙ ПРИ ОСТРОМ ГНОЙНОМ ОДОНТОГЕННОМ ОСТИТЕ У ДЕТЕЙ (ОБЗОР
ЛИТЕРАТУРЫ)****АННОТАЦИЯ**

Острый гнойный одонтогенный периостит челюстей представляет актуальную проблему в стоматологии и челюстно-лицевой хирургии. Среди детей с острыми одонтогенными воспалительными процессами челюстно-лицевой области значительную часть составляют больные с гнойным одонтогенным оститом. В настоящей статье приведен литературный обзор по этиологическим и патогенетическим механизмам развития данного заболевания, а также методов диагностики и современной тактики лечения больных с данной патологией.

Ключевые слова: Острый гнойный одонтогенный периостит, фармакотерапия, провоспалительные цитокины, патогенез, интерлейкин, воспалительный процесс.

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**БОЛАЛАРДА ЎТКИР ЙИРИНГЛИ ОДОНТОГЕН ОСТИТДА ЯЛЛИФЛАНИШ
АСОРАТЛАРИНИ ТАШХИСЛАШ ВА ДАВОЛАШНИНГ ЗАМОНАВИЙ КЎРИНИШИ
(АДАБИЁТЛАР ШАРХИ)**

АННОТАЦИЯ

Жағларнинг ўткир йирингли одонтоген периостити стоматология ва юз-жағ жарроҳлигида долзарб муаммо ҳисобланади. Юз-жағ соҳасининг одонтоген яллиғланиш жараёнлари орасида болаларда йирингли одонтоген остит билан касалланиш энг кўп қисми эгаллайди. Ушбу мақолада мазкур касалликнинг ривожланишининг этиологик ва патогенетик механизмлари, шунингдек диагностика усуллари ва ушбу патологияга эга беморларни даволашнинг замонавий тактикаси бўйича адабиётлар шарҳи берилган.

Калит сўзлар: Ўткир йирингли одонтоген периостит, фармакотерапия, яллиғланиш олди цитокинлари, патогенез, интерлейкин, яллиғланиш жараёни.

Relevance. The problem of increasing the number of children with acute odontogenic inflammatory diseases of the maxillofacial region has not lost its relevance. According to Panin A.M., Sukhanov A. E., Sementsov I. V. (2012) and other researchers, the issues of etiology, pathogenesis, clinic, diagnosis, prevention and treatment of odontogenic purulent-inflammatory diseases that have interested maxillofacial surgeons and dental surgeons around the world for many decades remain very relevant today [1,3,7,183,7,18].

In many cases, there is a change in the typical clinical picture and manifestations of this pathology in children, and insufficient effectiveness of the treatment despite the improvement of diagnostic methods [3].

Researchers have found that the frequency of acute purulent odontogenic ostitis of the jaw varies from 30% to 70% [5,6,14]. Rapidly progressing forms of the purulent process spread to several cellular spaces, including deep ones, are increasingly observed [1, 10]. The frequency of severe complications of acute-odontogenic infection is constantly increasing: mediastinitis, sepsis, infectious and toxic shock [2,9,189,18]. The influence of many factors and pathological conditions on the outcome after surgery in the maxillofacial region in children was studied, and the relationship between the cytokine system and the humoral immunity of the body in the oral cavity was traced. However, in the current literature, studies on the pathogenesis of acute purulent odontogenic ostitis of the jaw in children and the development of new pharmacotherapy methods based on this pathology's mechanism of action are rare [4,7].

It should be noted that in the literature of recent years, the frequency of research into the study of this problem has increased, the reason for this is the increase in the number of patients with acute odontogenic inflammatory diseases of the jaw among children. Often among children there is a severe, progressive course of this pathology, complicated by inflammatory processes, sepsis, septic shock. The main exogenous etiological factor of the maxillofacial region's inflammatory diseases in most cases is odontogenic microflora [11,15,16].

Despite particular successes achieved in treating acute purulent odontogenic inflammatory diseases of the jaw and their complications, the mortality rate continues to be high, indicating the need for early diagnosis, prognosis of the course and effective treatment of this pathology. Many researchers working with purulent odontogenic inflammatory diseases of the maxillofacial region indicate that one of the etiological factors of inflammatory diseases in this area is odontogenic infection, i.e. the spread of a microbial agent from the tooth cavity during complications of caries, first into the periapical periodontium (periodontitis), and then through multiple small holes in the cortical plate of the hole of the tooth into the medullary spaces of the alveolar process [4,9,21,24]. The causative agent of acute odontogenic infection in the overwhelming case is Staphylococcus aureus or Staphylococcus aureus, more often in the form of mono-infection or in combination with other coccoid flora, for example, Streptococcus.

Modern aspects of etiopathogenesis of acute purulent odontogenic ostitis. According to many researchers, epidermal staphylococcus and yeast-like fungi of the genus candida occupy a leading place in the etiology of odontogenic infectious and inflammatory diseases and their complications candida in monoculture and in associations today [19,25]. The revealed changes in the structure of pathogens of local inflammatory processes are confirmed by a high frequency of dysbiotic

changes in the microbiocenosis in the oral cavity, which is probably due to irrational antibiotic therapy and other factors listed above.

N. S. Lukoyanova et al. as a result of microbiological examination of patients with periodontitis, it was found that *Candida* fungi occur in the periapical granulomas in 63-67% of cases, in 7.9% of cases of *aspergillus*, in 16.6% of cases of penicilli, and in 12.5% of cases of yeast fungi [11].

Neutrophilic leukocytes phagocytize immune complexes and simultaneously damage the cell membrane, which leads to the release of lysosomal enzymes, inflammatory mediators [6, 15]. This is accompanied by platelet factor 3 activation and can cause intravascular coagulation, leading to microcirculation disorders and tissue necrosis [20, 24].

According to some researchers, the described immunopathological reaction also occurs in the pathogenesis of odontogenic infection. The role of an antigen is played by microbial waste products, structural elements of a microbial cell released after its death [17]. This interpretation of one of the links in the pathogenesis of odontogenic infection allows us to understand why many patients have non-pathogenic microbes as the causative agent of the disease. Often, a violation of the established balance between the infectious focus and the patient's body can cause a worsening of inflammatory phenomena and spread the infectious process beyond its initial boundaries [23].

First of all, these reasons include an increase in the virulence of microflora (pathogenicity test) due to a violation of the exudate outflow pathways through the root canal due to accidental ingestion of food masses into the carious cavity or deliberate obturation of its filling material. In the infectious focus, the concentration of microbes, their toxins and tissue degradation products increases, which, according to the laws of diffusion and osmosis, begin to penetrate to a greater extent through the connective tissue capsule into adjacent tissues [13]. Here, they can directly damage tissue structures or, penetrating the vascular bed and forming immune complexes, cause the development of a reaction like the Arthus-Sakharov phenomenon, i.e., a local inflammatory process with alteration phenomena [15, 18].

Another mechanism of imbalance between the chronic focus of odontogenic infection and the patient's body is associated with mechanical damage to the connective tissue capsule, accompanied by increased permeability [21]. This can occur when a tooth is removed due to chronic periodontitis, when the tooth is sharply overloaded during chewing solid food, when solid foreign bodies get into the food. The pressure experienced by the tooth is transmitted to the infectious focus and through the fluid filling the intercellular spaces to the connective tissue capsule. Damage to the connective tissue capsule under the influence of mechanical trauma, hydrodynamic shock, and an increase in its permeability are accompanied by the spread of microbes, their toxins, and tissue degradation products beyond the infectious focus [3,4].

It is known that the occurrence of acute odontogenic inflammatory diseases of the maxillofacial region is often preceded by the impact of various general factors on the patient's body: cooling, overheating, physical and emotional overstrain [10,19,10, 19].

The influence of such diverse effects on the course of the local infectious process can be explained by the fact that all of them cause patients to develop a common stereotypical reaction - an activation reaction that essentially corresponds to the first stage of stress, called the anxiety stage.

According to Solov'ev A. M., Faustov A. JI. A., Brennan M. T., Baltensperger M., (2008), the development of purulent-inflammatory diseases of the maxillofacial region requires the interaction of at least two factors: endogenous (internal) and exogenous (external) [11,15,23,25]. Endogenous factors include indicators of non-specific and immune defense of the macroorganism, and exogenous factors include bacterial agents and products of their vital activity, when virulent forms of the latter enter in "critical" concentrations. Thus, based on the above, we can conclude that one of the reasons for violating the natural immune barrier, which is expressed in the development of an inflammatory process that prevents the spread of infection, is immunodeficiency of varying severity [9, 12].

The role of neuropeptides in developing aggravation of the clinical course of acute purulent odontogenic otitis. In the last decade, more and more data have been published on the crucial role of neurotransmitters in regulating and maintaining the inflammatory response, and the

mediators used to implement the interaction of immune-competent and nerve cells have been identified [7,217, 21].

According to Hokfelt T, Pernow B, and Wahren J. (2021) "... substance P (SP), a neurotransmitter of noncholinergic nerves, is currently considered as the main neurogenic inflammatory mediator capable of causing pathophysiological reactions such as pain, mucosal oedema, and mucus hypersecretion [15]. Johnson J.F. (2019) states that "... neurogenic inflammation involving SP accompanies and exacerbates pre-existing inflammation in the CHLO initiated by an infectious agent" [15,16].

SP has a wide range of biological activity and can directly and indirectly affect the development of an inflammatory response. Immediate action is primarily associated with the effect on the vascular bed. SP stimulates the proliferation of endothelial cells, which leads to increased angiogenesis. In addition, SP has a vasodilating effect, increasing capillary permeability, which leads to a vascular reaction. In this case, postcapillary venules are involved in the process, which are responsible for the adhesion of lymphocytes and their migration to the focus of inflammation. The indirect effect of SP is associated with the activation of mast cells, eosinophils, macrophages, and lymphocytes. The existence of receptors for substance P on mastocytes, polynuclears, macrophages, and keratinocytes has been proven. Substance P induces the production of cytokines IL-1, -6, -12 by macrophages, IL-1 by keratinocytes IL-2, -4, -10, interferon- γ by T lymphocytes and causes degranulation of mast cells with the release of leukotrienes, prostaglandins, histamine, tNF- α , and nerve growth factor (pRF). In turn, inflammatory mediators (IL-1, tNF- α) lead to the release of neuropeptides from sensory nerve endings, increasing the level of SP [14,19,23]

In the works of M. V. Blikyan (2013), it was proved that acute odontogenic inflammatory diseases of the lower jaw are characterized by changes in the nerve by the type of inflammatory (infectious) neuropathy, while acute odontogenic osteomyelitis of the lower jaw is characterized by changes of a compression – ischemic nature. In this situation, acute somatic pain involves humoral factors of innate immunity in the allogenic process: lysozyme activity in the peripheral blood increases, the content of INF- γ and C-reactive protein increases, and lysozyme is intensively involved in the process. In acute somatic pain, the content and ratio of cytokines changes: the content of pro-inflammatory cytokines IL-1 α , IL-1P, IL-2, IL-6 increases; the range of IL-2 increases most significantly. At the initial stages of acute somatic pain formation, the content of the anti-inflammatory cytokine IL-10 decreases and remains reduced in the dynamics of the entire experiment [20].

Thus, successful resolution of inflammation requires an effective system of immunosuppression of its key cells, such as neutrophils, which generally undergo apoptosis, after which they are recognized and absorbed by macrophages. Dysregulation of this process contributes to the chronization of inflammatory diseases. The disclosure of the role of the immune system as a protective response against pathogens and in maintaining the pathological process created prerequisites for revising tactical treatment regimens for slow-moving purulent-inflammatory diseases of the maxillofacial region with a focus on immunocorrection [19,21,23].

Drug treatment and prevention of complications in acute purulent odontogenic otitis.

Acute purulent otitis is the main complication of chronic periodontitis. Complex treatment of acute purulent odontogenic otitis includes: opening the abscess, creating a free outflow for purulent exudate, removing the "causal" tooth (according to indications). After surgical intervention, both local and general antibacterial and anti-inflammatory treatment is indicated [10, 12].

According to some authors, Serrata is the drug of choice in the complex treatment of patients with acute purulent odontogenic diseases in the maxillofacial region [10]. Serratiopeptidase is a proteolytic enzyme with fibronolytic and decongestant properties, it also reduces the pain symptom by blocking the release of pain amines from the inflammatory focus. As a result of the hydrolysis of bradycardine, histamine and serotonin, serratiopeptidase reduces dilatation of capillaries and affects their permeability. It blocks plasmin inhibitors, thus promoting the fibrinolytic activity of plasmin. In the areas of inflammation, serratiopeptidase gets into the exudate and has a fibrinolytic effect [21].

In the work of Shcheplev B. V. [12], based on a morphological study of

microlymphocirculation in the gum, the effectiveness of lymphotropic administration of lincomycin in acute purulent odontogenic ostitis was shown. This treatment method can reduce the wound healing time by removing substances from the tissues that initiate or support an acute inflammatory reaction.

In the current conditions of "pharmacological oversaturation" of the body, reduced sensitivity of microflora to antibiotics, suppression of immune protection by environmental factors, and allergization of the body, conventional treatment methods have low efficiency [61]. Mubarakova L. N. [17] suggests for the treatment of acute purulent ostitis, immunostimulating multivitamin complexes "Complevit", "Multivit", "Vinibis", which stimulate non-specific protective reactions of the body, actively affect the immune system, catalyzing and regulating biochemical processes.

One of the main disadvantages of wound healing therapy is that many of the pharmacological preparations have a weak therapeutic effect, as a result of which the microflora is not entirely suppressed, the inflammatory process is slowly delimited and the wound is cleaned of purulent-necrotic masses [14]. Methods of sorption and application therapy to clean wounds from microorganisms and their waste products have an undoubted advantage.

Galimov R. A. [16] offers the sorbent "Coelofom" for treating purulent wounds, which accelerates wound cleansing, stops local signs of inflammation, and protects reparative processes. Filippova L. A. et al. [12, 14] suggest using an ozonated chlorhexidine solution at a concentration of 5 mg/l for 10 minutes to sanitize the wound to treat acute purulent odontogenic ostitis. The author notes that the proposed treatment method leads to a significant reduction or complete rehabilitation of the focus of purulent inflammation. Accelerates reparative processes in the wound.

Based on the above, a relatively large arsenal of techniques and tools for preventing and treating ostitis has been proposed. However, all these recommendations do not consider the vital role of yeast-like fungi in the development of the disease and, therefore, do not contain relevant recommendations with an etiological and pathogenetic focus. It should also be noted that most drugs and techniques used to prevent and treat ostitis do not consider current trends in changing the bacterial landscape not only in the tissues and contents of the mouth as a whole, but also directly in the wound itself.

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VOLUME 4, ISSUE 5

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